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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF PRE-OPERATIVE AND POST-
OPERATIVE JAUNDICE LEVEL USING PTCD REDUCTION
TECHNIQUE FOR AE****Muhammad Ali, Fan Hai Ning, Yang Dan Cai Rang, Waseem Sami Malik,
Raees Ahmad, Muhammad Shoaib Tahir**
Qinghai University Affiliated Hospital**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To assess the pre and post-operative jaundice level clinical efficacy and safety of an advanced percutaneous trans-hepatic cholangio-drainage to organize the alveolar echinococcosis patients and to prevent further liver damage and improve quality of life. Sustain bile flow to avoid jaundice and get ready patient for surgery.

Method: The data of 47 patients who underwent PTCD to minimize the jaundice level for surgery. After decrease yellow discoloration, the patients go through surgery for the AE lesion. The patients were examined for instant adverse events together with hemorrhage, perforation, pancreatitis, and cholangitis. We used paired t-test for statics analysis of data, during the two-year follow-up, they were observed for the reappearance of jaundice and AE.

Results: Bilirubin levels considerable decline in 47 patients significantly ($P < 0.05$). Common bile duct mild bleeding and infection occurred in patient. No severe adverse measures, having pancreatitis or perforation of the gastrointestinal or common bile duct occurred.

Conclusion: Sequential PTCD is safe and effective for the patient AE with jaundice. This method is responsible for low-risk quantity, fast to attain the preferred effect related complications produced by less active and to get better the patient liver function, recover the patient's quality of life has accomplished good clinical effect.

Keywords: Alveolar Echinococcosis (AE), Hydatid Alveolar Echinococcosis (HAE), Percutaneous trans-hepatic cholangio-drainage (PTCD), Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Total bilirubin (TB), Albumin (ALB), White Blood Cell (WBC) and Red Blood Cell (RBC).

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1-INTRODUCTION:

Alveolar echinococcosis is measured as one of the most hazardous parasitic zoonosis occurring in the northern hemisphere. The natural life cycle of the parasite is continued by definitive hosts shedding eggs with the feces and the following consumption of these eggs by appropriate intermediary hosts. Definitive hosts turn out to be infected by ingestion intermediary hosts, in which the metacestode stage progresses. Carnivores, in precise the red fox in Europe and the raccoon dog amongst natural world, over and above the dog and to a smaller amount the cat, signify definitive hosts for the parasite [1]. In additional epidemiological situations, for example, in China, dogs might, in accumulation toward foxes, show a significant role in the spread of AE [2]. Slight rodents, mostly voles, work for as regular intermediary hosts.

Humans remain atypical intermediary hosts and are presenting pretentious by the metacestode stage of the parasite. They turn out to be diseased through the consumption of Echinococcus multilocularis eggs. Subsequently, a preliminary asymptomatic incubation period of several years, humans might progress AE, which can remain deadly if left untreated [3]. Analysis of possible HAE is established on imaging methods such as abdominal ultrasound, magnetic resonance, and computed tomography in addition to the discovery of precise serum antibodies [4].

Along with the development of ultrasound device and ultrasonic interventional diagnosis and treatment technology, ultrasonic liver HAE patients become the preferred inspection scheme, for hepatic blood flow analysis has excellent advantages and shortcut, economy the ultrasound liver hydatid lesion more scans show substantial lesions a guide after the shadow shape present diversity and with very close beside the organization and hydatid lesion presents the calcification area draw lessons from these characteristics be roughly divided into four categories, Massive type, number of diffuse nodule calcification, liquefaction necrosis type giant block more present in the liver more small circular, irregular calcifications rear should be apparent failure carbon acoustic shadow growing on the interstate is infection small calcified lesions can be together then invaded show a more massive amount of new leaves formed but soft diffuse nodular type is in the same group several enough to due focal calcified the calcification [5].

At present, there are many methods of the biliary flow used in medicine, among which PTC is the more effective minimally invasive force method. Bile duct injuries can crucial toward bile leakage, intra-abdominal inflammations, cholangitis, and

secondary biliary cirrhosis owing to long-lasting strictures. Post-operative biliary leakages typically happen through the difficulty of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Dependent on the sort of wound, managing might contain percutaneous, endoscopic and open surgical involvements. They remain frequently cured through means of both surgical repair and endoscopic biliary drainage [6-7]. Surgical repair and endoscopic managing stay, famous specific cases, moreover tricky or ineffective, predominantly in patients by huge post-operative biliary duct faults. In these circumstances, the bile stream can be sidetracked away from the defect in the bile duct over percutaneous trans-hepatic biliary drainage [8-12].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

From March 2016 to November 2019, 47 successive patients with HAE with obstructive jaundice (demonstrated by USG, CT, MRI, and laboratory) underwent PTCD in our Qinghai University affiliated Hospital [Table 1]. The hospital ethics team agreed on this retrospective study and all patients on condition that on paper informed consent. This study included seventeen men and thirty-seven women aged 19 to 53 years, with a mean age of 37.4 ± 3 years old. All patients had obstructive jaundice and alveolar echinococcosis with the lesion in right liver 23 (48.9%), left liver 14 (29.8%) and both right and left liver 10 (21.3%). One (2.1%) patient were <5cm lesion and forty-six (97.9%) were >5cm. Eighteen (38.3%) patients with a massive lesion, eight (17.02%) with a nodular lesion, eight (17.02%) with liquefied lesion and thirteen (27.7%) with a mixed lesion. AE metastasis to lung seven (14.9%) and one (2.12%) with metastasis to the brain. PTCD was repeated in two patients because of overlooked common bile duct obstruction. Laboratory values, including total bilirubin (TB), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Albumin (ALB), WBC count and RBC count, were obtained using routine laboratory tests.

(1) Alveolar echinococcosis with signs and symptoms diagnosed by imaging and pathological examination; (2) Patients accompanied by obstructive jaundice; (3) Patients with common bile duct obstruction. (1) Patient other forms of echinococcosis; (2) Patient without biliary obstruction; (3) Patient without obstructive jaundice; (4) Patients concomitant with other diseases.

PTCD technique:

PTCD punctured the bile duct with an aseptic technique under ultrasound guidance and a particular anesthesia area. Cholangiography has shown the cystic duct junction and the common duct stones that can be organized near to the

anterior and posterior junctions of the right hepatic duct, because of the sufficient length of the catheter were pierced inside the duct there is less chance of catheter escaping. A 12 Fr (4.17mm) pigtail drainage catheter set was placed for the drainage of bile. It is a one-step procedure in which we remove the tighten cannula from a catheter and the distal part of the catheter is wet before placement then cleans the catheter before use, secure suture locking mechanism at the proximal site. Slide pigtail straightener along with the distal side of the thin flexible tube to flatten curl before placing stiffening cannula into the thin flexible tube. Place the stiffening cannula into the thin flexible tube and squeeze the Luer lock fitting. Eradicate pigtail straightener as of catheter before insertion. Cannula

assembles over proper guidewire and progress into the biliary system. Separate stiffening cannula from the catheter then carries on catheter over a guidewire into wanted location. The catheter accommodates a 0.038" (0.97mm) wire. The location has to be confirmed by imaging (Figure A). Once the location is confirmed, remove the cannula also guidewire. To hold the suture, replace the suture locking mechanism to the most distal site and then press the suture locking mechanism into the hub to secure it; after that, it has locked into the desired location (Figure B) and now the catheter ready to connect with a drainage bag (Figure C). The average time was (25±11) min and 24h bile flow for ml (505±113).

Figure A catheter pierced the skin and hydatid lesion shown in liver.
Qinghai university affiliated hospital with permission

Figure B catheter location confirmed by imaging
Qinghai university affiliated hospital with permission

Figure C insertion of a guidewire with 4Fr
Qinghai university affiliated hospital with permission

Surgery for AE:

To prepare for surgery patient should not eat and drink for 12h. According to the CT scan location and size of the lesion were marked for surgical incision, which explores the lesion site for surgery to view with Kocher's incision from the right rib margin. Make sure by removal of the intra-hepatic lesion, the remaining structural and functional parts of the liver work appropriately with minimizing the bleeding and tissue damage. During operation, the hepatic blood flow technique was used to control bleeding. An ultrasonic suction knife used to detach lesion from the healthy liver side by side electric knife was used for hemostasis. After complete/semi-hepatic resection of the liver, the surrounding damaged blood vessel, biliary tract and biliary bowel should be anastomosis. At last biliary tract and hemorrhage in the liver wound examination should be done. Under the diaphragm, the peritoneal drainage tube and T-tube should be kept. The average duration for surgery (290 ± 30) minutes and duration of hospital stay (33 ± 9) days.

Outcome measures:**RESULTS:**

Outcome recorded included postoperative hospital stay, success rate, cause of failure and procedure-related complications. The ALT, TB, ALB, WBC and RBC were recorded before the procedure and at one week after the procedure. Short-term adverse effects such as biliary duct infection, hemorrhage, pancreatitis and gastrointestinal and common bile duct perforation were assessed before discharging. Computed tomography and lab IgG, TB, WBC and ALT were performed at 3, 7, 14 and 24 after the procedure. Obstruction of common bile duct and recurrence of HAE, considered as long-term complications, were monitored for two years.

Statistical analysis:

All statistical analyses were achieved using IBM SPSS 22.0. Categorical variables were offered as number and percentage. Continuous data were offered as mean $\pm$ average. We used paired *t*-tests for similar indexes before and after the procedure in a similar patient. A *P* value of less than 0.05 was measured as statistically significant.

Table 1 Patient and treatment characteristics

Characteristics	N(%)
No. of patients	47
Gender	
Male	17(36.2)
Female	30(63.8)
Number of PTCD procedure	
One	45(95.7)
Two	2(4.3)
Location of AE	
Right liver	23(48.9)
Left liver	14(29.8)
Both	10(21.3)
Size classification of Lesion AE	
<5cm	1(2.1)
>5cm	46(97.9)
Lesion features	
Massive	18(38.3)
Nodular	8(17.02)
Liquefied	8(17.02)
Mixed	13(27.7)
Metastasis of AE	
Lung	7(14.9)
Brain	1(2.12)

Table 2 Relevant variable before and one week after PTCD

Item	Before PTCD	1w after PTCD
ALT (U/L)	140 ± 40	95.6 ± 20
TB (µmol/L)	130 ± 17.1	87.8 ± 8.8
ALB (g/L)	32.4 ± 5.1	30 ± 3.4
RBC (cells/mcL)	4.1 ± 0.93	3.6 ± 3.4
WBC (cells/mcL)	7.8 ± 1.8	6.7 ± 1.2

A total of 47 patients were successfully recovered from obstructive jaundice by PTCD in 45 (95.7%) of the 47 patients. PTCD was repeated in two patients. Massive lesion (38.3%), nodular lesion (17.02%), liquefied lesion (17.02%) and mixed lesion of AE (27.7%) (Table 1). The concentration of ALT, TB, ALB, WBC and RBC count declined significantly after PTCD. The differences in these indexes before PTCD and one week after PTCD were all significant ($P < 0.05$) while WBC ($P > 0.05$) [Table 2]

Nineteen (40.4%) of the forty-seven patients developed mild bleeding in common bile duct which usual treatment with 1000IU of reptilase and drainage clamping and *Escherichia coli* was found in the common bile duct, and a biliary duct infection was established. No severe adverse events occurred during the perioperative period, including pancreatitis or perforation of the gastrointestinal or common bile duct.

DISCUSSION:

The blockage in the bile duct causes a rise in bilirubin levels (obstructive jaundice). Common causes of obstructive jaundice contain gallstones in the biliary duct and tumors of the pancreas or bile duct. The occurrence of pancreatic cancer is about 10 per 100000 population in Western Europe [13]. The occurrence of gallbladder cancer is 1 in 100000 population [14]. If it is not controlled in a well-timed manner, it could be source lots of opposing events such as cholangitis, delay tumor management, poor quality of life and rising death rate, etc. Successful biliary drainage can considerably recover prognosis in patients with malignant obstructive jaundice [15]. Several different methods for the management of simultaneous gallbladder and CBD stones have been proposed and are currently in clinical use.[16-18].

Biliary infection is peak common difficulties in patients with malignant obstructive jaundice, and the main reason for death pre-operation [19]. An earlier report, the prevalence of infection after drainage in malignant obstructive jaundice is 14% - 47%, cholestasis produced through biliary

obstruction is beneficial to the bacteria breeding and increase bilirubin levels is easy for bacterial translocation, intestinal flora and intestinal mucosa barrier damage [19].

Though, we conducted a retrospective study to determine the efficacy of patients who can't bear surgical operation due to hepatic insufficiency; that is why we perform PTCD to decrease jaundice level and stable patient for AE surgery. PTBD is now very useful as a pain-relieving technique for patients with obstructive jaundice, which could not only reduce yellow discoloration as well as recover liver function and increase survival time, it can also be used as pre-operative drainage, offer certain circumstances for subsequent treatment [20]. Our study indicates that PTCD is safe and effective and has a low incidence of common bile duct infection and bleeding deprived of producing pancreatitis or puncture of the gastro-intestinal. Bilirubin level reduces significantly shows ($P < 0.05$), liver function index decrease with P value of ($P < 0.05$), albumin level decrease significantly with value of ($P < 0.05$), WBC level decline but still shows ($P > 0.05$) and RBC level shows significant value of ($P < 0.05$) after PTCD.

Several key points of PTCD:

(1) Puncture site should be from right front hepatic duct to achieve an extra capable tract; (2) Stiff guidewire is essential to end the puncture tract of CBD; (3) Aspiration concluded from a guide catheter; and (4) post-operative drainage decompresses the bile duct and reduce the occurrence of pancreatitis. Our study has two fundamental limits. First, as an experimental study, the number of patients was small. Second, this treatment technique is planned for a precise subclass of the patient in which it has been fine verified.

CONCLUSION:

Our data indicate that sequential PTCD is a safe, feasible, and effective treatment option for the patient having HAE with obstructive jaundice. In the first stage of PTCD, the second stage of radical resection, it is an alternative procedure for a patient who cannot directly undergo surgery without

PTCD. This technique provides low-risk coefficient, fast to achieve the desired effect related complications caused by less effective and to improve the patient liver function, improve the patient's quality of life have achieved good clinical effect.

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